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Teaching other Communication Skills than Writing and Presenting – A Take Home Workshop created as part of the PREFER Project

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Conference key areas: curriculum development, engineering skills

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Motivation: Participants will be able to test-drive a new curriculum element developed to have engineering students experience and reflect on the importance of effective verbal and visual communication.

Rationale: Although engineering education has been engaged to stimulate students communication skills, it is still very focused on oral presentations and written reports. For this reason, a new 1h communication activity was developed as part of the PREFER Project, an Erasmus+ Knowledge Alliance. This activity is called *Chinese Whisper with a Twist* because it is based on the Chinese Whisper game which aims at passing around a message. However, a Twist was applied to this activity and participants are constrained to either describe an image provided, listen and reply, or ask questions to draw the image. Thus, this activity allows participants to experience a wide spectrum of ways to communicate, such as describing, listening, questioning, answering, and drawing, as well as to create awareness and reflect on effective communication. More information about the activity can be found in [1].

Participant engagement: In this session, participants will be immersed in a hands-on experience of the communication activity. As such, they will be invited to work in small groups and challenged to play the *Chinese Whisper with a Twist*, i.e. to communicate effectively to reconstruct an image.

In the final part of the workshop, we will jointly reflect on how valuable this activity was for the participants, how it can be used to develop students communication skills and how participants could integrate it into their engineering courses.

The participation is limited to a maximum number of 30 people.

Takeaway: The attendees will gain a curriculum element, ready for implementation in their own courses. Not only will they have the opportunity to experience the education activity, but also obtain practical suggestions to integrate the activity from its creators. Participants will be given access to the full teaching implementation kit after the workshop as an Open Educational Resource.

Significance for engineering education: This workshop will provide educators with a short 1h practical educational curriculum element to enhance students' communication skills that can be applied in almost any course in any engineering degree programme.

Reference:

[1] Leandro Cruz, M., and G.N. Saunders-Smiths, "Design and Implementation of New Communication and Lifelong Learning elements in a Master Engineering Course", 46th SEFI Annual Conference, 2018.